

Synthesis and crystal structure of copper(II) complex with Schiff base from salicylaldehyde and 1,2-phenylenediamine

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Abstract : A new complex [Cu(saloph)]{[Cu(salobp)₂]Cl} (1) was synthesized by the reaction of CuCl and the Schiff base ligand (saloph) derived from salicylaldehyde and 1,2-phenylenediamine. Under hydrothermal conditions, in the presence of Cu^I ion and methanol, saloph is converted into the benzimidazole ligand (salobp). The single crystal X-ray diffraction analyses reveal that 1 contains discrete [Cu(saloph)] (A), [Cu(salobp)₂]Cl (B) in the asymmetric unit. In A, the geometry around the Cu^{II} is almost square planar with two nitrogens and two oxygens from saloph providing the tetradentate coordination, while in B, the geometry around the Cu^{II} is linear with two nitrogens from two different monodentate benzimidazole ligands (salobp).

Keywords : Crystal structures, copper complexes, salicylaldehyde, Schiff base.

Introduction

In the past decades, the transition metal complexes containing quadridentate Schiff base ligands have been extensively investigated due to their novel structures and potential applications in many fields¹⁻³. Particularly, a large number of transition metal complexes of salen [salen²⁻ = *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneaminato)] and saloph [saloph²⁻ = *N,N'*-*o*-phenylenebis(salicylideneaminato)] derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and various primary amines have been the subject of a number of investigations⁴⁻⁷, such as chelates of salen and saloph containing cobalt(II) are known for their dioxygen uptake capabilities^{8,9}, while those of chromium, manganese, iron, nickel, oxovanadium and copper act as versatile catalysts for oxidation and hydroformylation reactions¹⁰⁻¹³. On the other hand, in refluxing ethanol, "salen" type Schiff base ligand is converted into the benzimidazole ligand (salobp), but its' metal complexes are rare¹⁴. Therefore, herein, we report the synthesis and X-ray crystal structure of a new copper complex containing either the Schiff base ligands from the condensation reaction of salicylaldehyde and 1,2-phenylenediamine, or its benzimidazole ligand, as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. 2-[[2-[[*Z*]-{(2-Hydroxyphenyl)methylidene}amino]phenyl]imino]methyl]phenol (saloph), 2-[[2-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-1*H*-benzimidazole-1-yl]methyl]phenol (salobp).

Results and discussion

Under hydrothermal conditions, in the presence of Cu^I ion and methanol, saloph is converted into the benzimidazole ligand salobp (Scheme 1), in which, one phenolic substituent is linked directly to the central carbon of the benzimidazole group and the other via a CH₂ group to a nitrogen atom. This type of transformation is well known in the case of other substituted benzimidazoles with two phenolic substituents¹⁴.

An ORTEP view of the asymmetric unit containing two molecules [Cu(saloph)] (A) and [Cu(salobp)₂]Cl (B)

for **1** is shown in Fig. 1 along with atom numbering scheme. Important bond lengths and angles are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of complex **1**.

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of complex **1**.

The molecular geometry and conformations of **A** and **B** are different. In **A**, similar to copper(II) complex with saloph, the geometry around the copper is almost square planar with two nitrogens and two oxygens from saloph²⁻ providing the tetradentate coordination. The mean bond distance of Cu–N and Cu–O are 1.947(3) and 1.900(3) Å, respectively, and the bite angle N(1)–Cu–N(2) is 84.41(13)°, which compares well with the structures of substituted Cu(salen) and other saloph complexes³.

In the case of molecule **B**, the geometry around the copper is linear with two nitrogens from two different monodentate benzimidazole ligands (salobp). The bond distances of Cu(2)–N(3) and Cu(2)–N(3A) are the same [1.854(3) Å], and the bond angle of N(3)–Cu–N(3A) is 180.00, indicating the linear geometry of copper(I), which is rare in the available literatures¹⁴.

The molecules are packed almost parallel to diagonal directions in the *a-b* plane and are held together by van der Waals forces, and the hydrogen bonding interactions involved phenol and chlorine, such as O(3)–H(3O)···Cl [3.006(3) Å], O(4)–H(4)···O(1) [2.854(4) Å] and O(4)–H(4)···O(2) [2.994(4) Å] (Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms : #1; -x+1, -y+1, -z+2).

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde and 1,2-phenylenediamine were purchased from Aldrich and Co. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade and were used as supplied.

Synthesis of 2-{[(2-{(Z)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene)amino}phenyl)imino]methyl}phenol (saloph): The Schiff base ligand, 2-{[(2-{(Z)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene)amino}phenyl)imino]methyl}phenol (saloph), was prepared

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for complexes **1**

Bond	Dist.	Bond	Dist.	Bond	Dist.
Cu(1)–O(1)	1.887(3)	Cu(1)–N(2)	1.947(3)	Cu(2)–N(3)	1.854(3)
Cu(1)–O(2)	1.914(3)	Cu(1)–N(1)	1.947(3)	Cu(2)–N(3A)	1.854(3)
Angle	(°)	Angle	(°)	Angle	(°)
O(1)–Cu(1)–O(2)	87.13(11)	C(14)–N(2)–C(13)	123.0(3)	C(1)–O(1)–Cu(1)	127.5(3)
O(2)–Cu(1)–N(2)	94.38(12)	C(13)–N(2)–Cu(1)	1120.(2)	C(8)–N(1)–Cu(1)	112.9(2)
O(2)–Cu(1)–N(1)	176.76(12)	C(27)–N(3)–Cu(2)	126.7(3)	C(14)–N(2)–Cu(1)	125.0(3)
N(3A)–Cu(2)–N(3)	180.000	O(1)–Cu(1)–N(2)	178.08(11)	C(27)–N(3)–C(28)	106.9(3)
C(20)–O(2)–Cu(1)	126.7(2)	O(1)–Cu(1)–N(1)	94.14(13)	C(28)–N(3)–Cu(2)	126.4(2)
C(7)–N(1)–Cu(1)	124.4(3)	N(2)–Cu(1)–N(1)	84.41(13)		

Symmetry codes : 1; x, y, -z+1/2; x+1/2, y+1/2, z; -x+1/2, y+1/2, -z+1/2, 2; -x+1/2, -y, z+1/2; -x, y+1/2, -z+1/2; x+1/2, -y+1/2, -z.

by standard methods¹⁵ i.e. ethanolic solution (46 ml) of salicylaldehyde (1 ml, 9.52 mmol) was slowly added to a solution of ethanol (30 ml) containing 1,2-phenylenediamine (0.52 g, 4.8 mmol). The mixture was gently heated for 3.5 h with vigorously stirring. The yellow precipitate obtained was filtered off and dried under vacuum. The yellow solid was dissolved in ethanol and kept at ambient environment. After two weeks, the yellow crystals were obtained upon slow evaporation at room temperature (yield 79%) (Found : C, 75.97; H, 5.13; N, 8.94. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{16}N_2O_2$: C, 75.93; H, 5.10; N, 8.86%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3443(s), 1615(s), 1585(m), 1562(s), 1480(m), 1277(s), 1193(m), 1151(m), 1113(w), 909(s), 857(m), 830(m), 810(m), 760(m), 640(w), 581(w), 5.16(w).

Synthesis of [Cu(saloph)]{[Cu(salobp)₂]Cl} (1) : 2-[(3-((E)-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)methylidene)amino)phenyl]-

heated at 55 °C for three days to give dark rod-like crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction analysis (yield 67%) (Found : C, 64.54; H, 4.03; N, 7.65. Calcd. for $C_{80}H_{60}ClCu_3N_8O_8$: C, 64.60; H, 4.07; N, 7.53%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3441(m), 1614(s), 1563(s), 1480(s), 1375(m), 1277(s), 1192(s), 1151(s), 1113(m), 910(s), 857(m), 830(m), 809(m), 760(s), 639(w), 581(w), 502(w), 438(w).

X-Ray crystallography : Crystallographic data for complex [Cu(saloph)]{[Cu(salobp)₂]Cl} (1) are given in Table 2. The diffraction data were collected at 293 K on a Siemens P4 CCD diffractometer with graphite monochromated Mo- K_{α} radiation (0.71073 Å). The structures were solved by using the program SHELXTL-97 package^{16,17} and Fourier difference techniques, and refined by full-matrix least-squares method on F^2 . All hydrogen atoms were added theoretically.

Table 2. Crystal data and refinements

Empirical formula	$C_{80}H_{60}ClCu_3N_8O_8$	Crystal size	$0.44 \times 0.32 \times 0.16$ mm
Crystal system	Monoclinic	θ (°)	1.77 to 25.00
Space group	$C2/c$	Limiting indices	$0 \leq h \leq 46$
a (Å)	39.012(12)		$0 \leq k \leq 8$
b (Å)	7.471(2)		$-35 \leq l \leq 27$
c (Å)	29.812(9)	Reflections collected/unique	6719/5898
α (°)	90	R (int)	0.0253
β (°)	129.54	Data/restraints/parameters	5898/0/456
γ (°)	90	Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.928
V (Å ³)	6701.9(4)	Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0466, 0.1015
Z	4	R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0813$, $wR = 0.1109$
ρ (g/cm ³)	1.474	Extinction coefficient	0.0004(4)
F (000)	3056	Largest diff. peak and hole (e.Å ⁻³)	0.0481 and -0.546

imino)methyl}phenol (saloph) (0.059 g, 0.2 mmol), CuCl (0.018 g, 0.2 mmol) and NaOH (0.01 g) were thoroughly mixed in a mortar with pestle, and placed in a 25 cm long thick-walled Pyrex tube. After addition of 2.5 mL of methanol, the tube was cooled with liquid N_2 , evacuated under vacuum and sealed with a torch. The tube was

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